

The Euratom NPHyCo project: Conceptualization, technical work plan and current status

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ABSTRACT

This manuscript provides an overview of the goals, technical content, and close-to-final status of the Euratom NPHyCo project. NPHyCo stands for Nuclear Powered Hydrogen Cogeneration, and its ultimate goal is the design and preparation of a large-scale (MW-range) hydrogen cogeneration facility coupled to a nuclear power plant (NPP), which can become operational in a short-term horizon. The project analyses the existing economic, technical, safety and regulatory considerations for NPP owners to produce nuclear hydrogen through several cases of study applied to selected NPP sites and European markets.

The manuscript summarizes the main outcomes as of December 2024 regarding the integration scenarios of a hydrogen production plant (HPP) into a NPP site, based on the coupling configuration and sharing of balance-of-plant components between facilities. Given the interest and degree of cooperation of the Ukrainian state operator Energoatom, most of the technical calculations are based on the specifications of Rivne and Khmelnytskyi NPPs, both powered with water-water energy reactor (VVER) technology.

The project has delineated a HPP configuration with an overall capacity of 45 MW. The safety assessment relies on deterministic and probabilistic methodologies, which are applied through numerical simulation tools. The results are mostly based on example scenarios. However, they allow to derive general conclusions. Deterministic calculations are applied to a hydrogen plant either in a container or building solution, to determine the optimal configuration and required safety measures upon an intended release of hydrogen and subsequent ignition, leading to a fire or explosion. The hazards of the worst-case scenario in the HPP towards safety-related NPP structures are evaluated based on onsite and offsite HPP integration at Rivne NPP, with the corresponding structural fragility criterion.

Abbreviations: AEL, Alkaline Electrolysis; BP, Business Plan; BWR, Boiling Water Reactor; CAPEX, Capital Expenses; DAM, Day-Ahead Markets; DC, Direct Current; HPP, Hydrogen Production Plant; HTE, High-Temperature Electrolysis; IRR, Internal Rate Of Return; KPI, Key Performance Indicator; LCOE, Levelized Cost Of Electricity; LCOH, Levelized Cost Of Hydrogen; LFL, Lower Flammability Limit; LTE, Low-Temperature Electrolysis; LTO, Long Term Operation; NPP, Nuclear Power Plant; OPEX, Operational Expenses; PEM, Proton Exchange Membrane; PPA, Power Purchase Agreement; PWR, Pressurized Water Reactor; RES, Renewable Energy Source; SOEC, Solid Oxide Electrolyser Cell; SAF, Sustainable Aviation Fuel; TRL, Technological Readiness Level; VCE, Vapour Cloud Explosion; VVER, Water-Water Energy Reactor; WP, Work Package.

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The techno-economic study addresses the hydrogen value chain, encompassing low-temperature and high-temperature electrolysis technologies, up to storage and transportation. The study evaluates if existing systems and resources at the NPP are sufficient and suitable to supply the HPP, and thereby lead to reduced capital expenses (CAPEX) and operational expenses (OPEX). A summary of techno-economic analysis is summarized in this paper. Several sensitivity analyses have served to obtain the configuration to minimize the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) and advance operational strategies to determine the best dynamic configuration for the hybrid system operation. A final business plan for hydrogen production by means of already existing NPPs, has been also developed. For the licensing of the HPP in the vicinity of the NPP, the degree of integration and distance between facilities are the most critical factors. The licensing impact is investigated for three different levels of plant integration.

1. Introduction

The Green Deal is the comprehensive European Union (EU) framework to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050. In a carbon-neutral economy, hydrogen produced by water electrolysis will play a major role to decarbonise energy-intensive industrial sectors and heavy-duty transportation difficult to electrify, as well as on energy storage applications. To achieve this goal, the EU Hydrogen Strategy forecasts 40 GW of electrolyser capacity by 2030, or an equivalent 10 million tonnes of green hydrogen. However, in 2023 about 90% of the hydrogen produced in the EU came from fossil-based sources, whereas less than 1% was produced by water electrolysis (see Fig. 1). To fill this gap, the Hydrogen Strategy recently acknowledged low-carbon hydrogen as a short-term solution to accelerate the hydrogen economy.

As of today, low-carbon hydrogen is mostly produced by steam-methane reforming with carbon capture (European Commission, 2024). The methane demand is mostly fulfilled by imports, which challenges independence of the EU energy supply. Since February 2022, the changes in the energy market and the ambitious decarbonisation goals have led to a nuclear renaissance within the EU. The European Commission recognizes in the REPowerEU framework the key role of nuclear in the EU to ensure energy supply security. Furthermore, nuclear power has been labelled by the EU Taxonomy as a low-carbon transition energy source (Lambert et al., 2024).

Besides the generation of low-carbon baseload electricity, nuclear power has the potential to generate massive amounts of low-carbon hydrogen by sharing thermal and electrical energy between the nuclear station and a hydrogen cogeneration facility (Verfondern et al., 2017). This approach has been already identified by several member states within the EU, among them France, which is evaluating through

the state-owned electricity company EDF the hybridization of NPPs for the generation of nuclear hydrogen through high-temperature electrolysis (HTE), aiming to a significant reduction of production costs (Py and Capitaine, 2006). Likewise, the US Department of Energy is considering HTE for the generation of nuclear hydrogen (EPRI, 2022; INL, 2023; SANDIA, 2020).

The Euratom NPHyCo Project: “Nuclear Powered Hydrogen Cogeneration” identifies the existing gap in low-carbon hydrogen generation with EU targets and addresses it through the investigation of short-term deployment of large-scale nuclear hydrogen capacities. NPHyCo was launched in September 2022 with a duration of 2.5 years. The project analyses the existing economic, technical, safety and regulatory considerations for NPP owners to produce nuclear hydrogen through several cases of study. The project aims at investigating the technical feasibility and economic viability of existing NPPs to generate large amounts of hydrogen to support the decarbonisation goals of the EU, and eventually to prepare the design of a pilot plant that can become operational in a short-term horizon (5–10 years).

In order to achieve this goal, NPHyCo sets three ambitious objectives.

- Assessment of the feasibility of hydrogen production at existing NPPs
- Assessment of the added value of hydrogen production at existing NPPs
- Identification of suitable pilot project locations

The project outcomes aim at demonstrating that nuclear hydrogen is not only technically and economically feasible, but also attractive compared to other hydrogen generation techniques. With this aim, suitable commercial light water reactors at available nuclear sites within Europe are evaluated in the project, together with available water electrolyser technologies. Plant integration is evaluated not only from a technical and licensing perspective but also from an economic point of view providing as a main output a business plan for the already existent NPPs in Europe. The technology scouting is summarized in decision matrixes, guidelines, and checklists, which are available to NPP operators, hydrogen production EPCs (engineering, procurement, and construction), and other stakeholders for their decision-making processes.

During the last decade numerous water electrolysis projects in the MW-scale have been achieved following the step forward in low-temperature technologies, namely Alkaline Electrolysis (AEL) and Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM). Both have reached a technological readiness level (TRL) 9 and are already deployed at a commercial scale (Lange et al., 2023). On the one hand, higher capacities lead to lower levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) due to a reduction in CAPEX of the cogeneration facility. On the other hand, the larger hydrogen inventories increase the complexity of the safety assessment with subsequent regulatory aspects. The most significant hazards of the hydrogen facility comprise fires (due to heat radiation) and explosions (due to overpressure) (IAEA, 2013).

The expected benefits of the integration of a hydrogen cogeneration facility into a NPP site are twofold: it generates an additional revenue source by the selling of hydrogen; whereas it reduces the negative

Fig. 1. Hydrogen production per source in the EU in 2023 (European Commission, 2024).

consequences over plant components relative to flexible operation in periods of high renewable energy penetration into the electrical grid, ensuring NPP operation at full load by ramping up and down power with the HPP (IAEA, 2018). In this regard, AEL and PEM technologies offer load-following capability and operational flexibility, which makes them suitable to be coupled to a nuclear station. Sharing balance-of-plant components may further reduce the LCOH. In upcoming years, high-temperature electrolysis is expected to grow substantially by efficiently using thermal energy as feedstock through Solid Oxide Electrolyser Cell (SOEC). The possibilities of sharing balance-of-plant components are displayed in Fig. 2.

The topic of nuclear hydrogen is developing quickly, since hydrogen is a prominent part of all European energy roadmaps. Besides NPHyCo, which relies on the operation of GEN II/III conventional nuclear reactors, the Sustainable Energy Technology Platform (SNETP) supports through the NC2I and NUGENIA initiatives further hydrogen cogeneration projects, such as GEMINI 4.0 (Fütterer et al., 2022), based on the operation of high temperature gas reactors, and TANDEM (Vaglio-Gaudard et al., 2024), which is based on the operation of small modular reactors, respectively. Constantin (2024) and Venizelou and Poulikkas (2024) may be consulted for reviews of the latest state of the art in nuclear hydrogen production.

The purpose of this manuscript is to provide a description of the NPHyCo project. The paper provides a brief overview of the methodology and consortium, highlighting the main scientific objectives and the overall methodology. The status and results of the project are reported in the paper, as well as the work performed. The manuscript is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the project methodology, structure, and work distribution. It also introduces the project consortium and partners' capabilities. Section 3 reports the project's main outcomes, whereas Section 4 provides conclusive remarks and an outlook of NPHyCo.

2. Project methodology and consortium

2.1. Methodology and structure

The methodological approach of NPHyCo comprises four main stages: (1) Data assessment, (2) gap analysis, (3) data processing and (4) user need-alignment. In the first stage, the required data comes from

Fig. 2. Possibilities of sharing of balance-of-plant components addressed in NPHyCo.

different sources; some information is publicly available, e.g., electrolyser plant designs, hydrogen prices, standards and guidelines, whereas other input data is confidential and thus only open to respective consortium partners, i.e., NPP design data or information on available utilities. Some data is also gathered from the Advisory Group Members or derived from related studies.

In the second stage, the gap analysis matches the amount, type, and quality of available data in order to answer three basic research questions; which preconditions, requirements and factors must be assessed when planning nuclear-powered hydrogen production with existing technologies?; what are the favourable preconditions, requirements and factors?; and what is the benefit that can be expected from a favourable case? The gap analysis informs the third stage what kind of data treatment (analysis, processing, transforming, clustering, partitioning) is needed to extract relevant information from the various data sets to answer the abovementioned research questions.

The project structure is displayed in Fig. 3. NPHyCo is divided into seven work packages (WPs) arranged into a top-bottom approach, where WP2 to WP4 run in parallel. The main WPs are.

- WP1: Conceptualization (led by Hunatom)
- WP2: Technical Roadmap (led by Framatome GmbH)
- WP3: Economic Roadmap (led by Tecnatom S.A.)
- WP4: Licensing Roadmap (led by NRG)
- WP5: Implementation Roadmap (led by ESG)
- WP6: Communication and Dissemination (led by Nucleareurope)
- WP7: Project Coordination (lead by Framatome GmbH)

In the data processing stage, the outcomes from each WP are assembled and then processed through developed tools and algorithms. The results are then brought into the right shape and form for the end users, as being the following output.

- Suitable locations and layout screened
- Decision matrix for EU nuclear stations
- Conceptual pilot plant integration design

2.2. Consortium and capabilities

The NPHyCo consortium includes industrial partners with solid knowledge and proven expertise in the design and layout of nuclear systems and large hydrogen electrolyser plants (e.g., Framatome, Tecnatom and Ansaldo). This expertise is complemented by the involvement of organizations that cooperate closely with the NPP operators (e.g., Hunatom and Energy Safety Group), which are in the position to facilitate the NPP design data needed for the various technical and regulatory assessments. The consortium includes research institutes and academia with expertise in nuclear and renewable energy research (CEA, GRS, NRG, TUD and CVR). Nucleareurope brings competences in communication and dissemination and takes care of the stakeholder management and socio-economic studies. In total, NPHyCo comprises 13 partners from 8 EU member countries and Ukraine (see Table 1).

Numerous scientific and industrial organizations were also invited to take part in the project as advisors and end-users of the obtained results. Those include EDF, CEZ, Energoatom, Hydrogen Europe, Fortum, TÜV, Elogen, EPRI, NET4GAS, KSB, CNAT, KKG, Xpo, etc. The participation of NPP operators, who in the future may be in a position to implement the results of NPHyCo, which currently provide feedback at different project stages has proven to be of great relevance for the project's progression.

2.3. Ambition of the project

NPHyCo is grounded on the changes in the energy system taking place in Europe. It relates to the rising share of renewable energy sources (RES) in the grid and the potential negative consequences for NPPs

Fig. 3. Project structure and work package description.

Table 1
List of organizations involved in the NPHyCo consortium.

Participant	Official name	Short	Country
1 (Coordinator)	Framatome GmbH	FRA-G	Germany
2	Ansaldo Nucleare S.p.A.	ANN	Italy
3	Ansaldo Energia S.p.A.	AEN	Italy
4	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives	CEA	France
5	Centrum Vyzkumu Rez Sro	CVR	Czech Republic
6	Energy Safety Group LLC	ESG	Ukraine
7	Nucleareurope	FOR	Belgium
8	Gesellschaft für Anlagen- und Reaktorsicherheit gGmbH	GRS	Germany
9	Nuclear Research and Consultancy Group	NRG	Netherlands
10	Tecnatom S.A.	TEC	Spain
11	Technische Universität Dresden	TUD	Germany
12	Hunatom Innovációs és Gazdaságfejlesztési Zrt	HUN	Hungary
13	European Commission Joint Research Centre	JRC	European Union

driven by the reduced income from nuclear-produced electricity due to an increasing demand to operate in load-follow or even flexible mode and an increasing rate of prices close to zero or even negative values at the energy spot market (meaning for an NPP that it operates below its operating costs). In addition, comparing the forecasted needs of RES with the actual situation displayed in Fig. 1, the need of short-term capacities for low-carbon hydrogen production becomes evident. NPHyCo identifies and addresses this gap by investigating realistic scenarios for large-scale low-carbon hydrogen production linked to already operating NPPs. The project outcomes are meant to be beneficial for the EU to support the ambitious decarbonisation goals of the Green Deal.

Decarbonisation goals have led to country-specific hydrogen roadmaps that forecast large low-carbon hydrogen demand within the next years. This background has shaped the project approach, which considers (not only but predominantly) mature hydrogen generation technologies (AEL and PEM) and existing NPP sites, to study the possibility to couple them for mutual benefit, and to be able to install large capacities to produce nuclear hydrogen within the next 5–10 years.

The successful achievement of the NPHyCo objectives could have the following positive impacts for the European nuclear industry and the transition into a green hydrogen driven future.

- Lowering of maintenance costs of the coupled NPP due to optimized generation mode of the NPP by less transients to the material
- Improvement of NPP fuel usage by omitting load-follow operations or part-load operation but using the surplus electricity for hydrogen generation instead
- Production of comparable large amount of green hydrogen for further usage and storage for mobility, heating, and reforming
- Reduced CAPEX/OPEX costs due to use of existing auxiliary systems and infrastructure
- Fulfilling the expected European demand of low-carbon hydrogen with alternative production methods

NPHyCo is funded the Euratom Research and Training Programme (2021–2025) and relates to the Innovation Action scheme. In this regard, the project innovates beyond the state of the art through; (a) assessing the potential for short-term deployment; (b) scrutinising the possible degree of integration; and (c) analysing the potential EU hydrogen market by comparing nuclear-hydrogen key performance indicators (KPIs) against other production technologies to test its competitiveness. The development of future plants and interest for the involved parts, e.g., investors, operators, and technology providers, is

addressed by preparing the templates and practical checklists for the pilot plant, and identifying technical, economic, operational barriers and drivers for coupling plants.

3. Project work plan and status

3.1. WP1: conceptualization

This WP has successfully been completed and the deliverables D1.1 “Project frame of reference” and D1.2 “Scenario definition” have already been issued. The former summarizes the needs and benefits of nuclear hydrogen in the current EU decarbonisation context. The deliverable D1.1 provides an assessment of available hydrogen generation technologies (AEL, PEM, and SOEC), as well as an evaluation of European NPP suitability and advantageous factors, including plant sites of VVER type.

External boundary conditions such as hydrogen storage, distribution and transport have been assessed, together with potential consumers, energy market price, and financial assistance for the NPP operation. The most significant conclusions are; (a) Water and steam electrolysis will be considered for further analysis; (b) AEL units are the most mature and durable systems nowadays. Said that, the consortium expects the situation to reverse in the upcoming years, with increasing TRL for PEM and SOEC technologies, and both are therefore accounted for in the project calculations; (c) transportation, storage and final uses shall be considered as part of the value chain of hydrogen production; and (d) it will be crucial to determine a competitive LCOH for the end users to ensure the viability of a future HPP.

The deliverable D1.2 summarizes the assessment of the levels of integration between the NPP and HPP, and ultimately the list of coupling scenarios to be investigated. Those scenarios have been defined after the investigation of the needs of the HPP, the possible levels of integration and locations, the NPP operational modes (e.g., base-load and flexible-load operation) and further assumptions.

The main needs of HPP are summarized as follows.

- Electricity in DC is the energy source for the electrolysis process
- Demineralized water with a high level of purity is the main consumable of the electrolytic production of hydrogen. In case of SOEC, the steam is the main consumable
- Cooling water and chilled water are required for cooling of the components and for hydrogen gas purification process
- Wastewater treatment is needed to remove the wastewater resulting from the HPP
- Pressurized air is used in the HPP for operation of pneumatic drives for valves
- The HPP needs nitrogen for purging purposes
- A respective safety environment needs to be established in the HPP

The list of eligible NPP sites was narrowed down to the following plants that are selected for further investigation in following WPs.

- Rivne and Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine (VVER)
- Trillo, Spain (PWR)
- Temelin and Dukovany, Czech Republic (VVER)
- Paks, Hungary (VVER)
- Gösgen, Switzerland (PWR)

It is intended to perform the analysis at least for one type of NPPs exemplarily, that is, one case of study for either VVER-440, VVER-1000, Boiling Water Reactor (BWR), or Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR). With the feedback of the Ukrainian state operator Energoatom regarding Khmelnytskyi and Rivne NPPs, the two VVER-type reactors are covered. For each NPP site all three electrolyser technologies (AEL, PEM, and SOEC) shall be considered.

The price of electricity is the main driver for the production cost of

hydrogen by low-temperature electrolysis (LTE). Currently, for SOEC it is CAPEX and in second place electricity also. A major benefit from coupling hydrogen production to nuclear electricity production is the potential to define the HPP as a part of the NPP and the respective electricity consumption as own consumption or home need in case internal production costs are lower than external grid prices for big consumers. The investigations carried out with operators of existing NPPs and from public available sources showed at an early stage that it is not possible to operate an industrial plant of any kind directly on the site of an NPP or in very close vicinity. On the other hand, respective exemptions may be possible to be granted if the feasibility and especially the safety of such coupled plants can be demonstrated.

The main conclusions from deliverable D1.2 can be summarized in four points; (a) Some of the needs of an HPP may be covered with already existing infrastructure of a coupled NPP; (b) the provision of electricity at a competitive price is understood as the minimal integration that any scenario should bear; (c) the price of electricity is the main parameter for the production cost of hydrogen from electrolysis, especially for LTE; and (d) the produced hydrogen needs to reach the consumer, therefore off-taker analysis and connection to the customer must be covered in the interface report.

The benefits of integration are expected to be higher with lesser distances within on-site solutions. Based on the investigation of the needs of a HPP, possible integration levels, as well as off-taker analysis, nine postulated integration scenarios have been defined, and are gathered in Table 2. Sharing of chilled water between both facilities has been dismissed after feedback from the NPP operators.

3.2. WP2: Technical Roadmap

The deliverable D2.1 “Analysis of viable interfaces within NPP environment for hydrogen cogeneration” provides an assessment of the needs of the HPP in terms of systems and components, and based on those requirements the general possibilities of integration have been inferred. The report includes European NPPs and specific sites, as well as consideration of hydrogen storage and transport. In this regard, one of the main outcomes of the investigation is the fact that in general no major off-takers (e.g., petrochemical industries, steelworks) are found in the vicinity of the European NPPs, and therefore transportation will constitute a significant aspect for hydrogen cogeneration, that needs to be addressed in the financial analysis.

Based on the available data from the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Gas (ENTSO-G) regarding the hydrogen infrastructure map, the study has been able to identify existing pipelines and corridors that may provide opportunities for transport in specific cases. After screening all eligible NPP sites, Rivne NPP was chosen as the reference nuclear facility in this WP to perform the case of study. It is located in the Rivne Oblast in Ukraine and comprises an overall turbine-generator output of 2880 MW. The NPP site hosts two reactor units powered by VVER-440/V-213 (440 MW), and two units powered by

Table 2

Pre-set of coupling scenarios to be investigated.

On-site solutions	Off-site solutions
Full integration except chilled water, with electricity at normal price (grid)	Integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity at normal price (grid)
Full integration except chilled water, with electricity at reduced price (home need)	Integration of electricity and cooling water with electricity at reduced price (home need)
Integration of electricity and cooling water only at normal price (grid)	Integration of electricity only at normal price (proximity of NPP and HPP)
Integration of electricity and cooling water only at reduced price (home need)	Integration of electricity only at reduced price (home need)
	Zero integration as benchmark, normal price (grid)

Fig. 4. Location of building sites in the two selected locations at Rivne NPP (aerial view taken from Google (2024)).

VVER-1000/V-320 (1000 MW). In the framework of NPHyCo, the state operator Energoatom has proposed two integration sites within the NPP site for a potential HPP integration, which are displayed in Fig. 4.

The reference HPP configuration is based on LTE with an overall capacity of 45 MW to proceed with the study and risk assessment. The electrolyser capacity accounts for 30 MW. The technical specifications have been defined for AEL and PEM technology based on corresponding mass and energy balance calculations. The electrolyser facility has a nominal capacity of 494 kg/h (as a result of the assumed electrolyser characteristics, cf. WP3). A 30 kg buffer tank is located adjacent to the electrolyser facility and stores gaseous hydrogen at 35 bar to decouple the operating regime of the electrolyser and the compressors from the high-pressure storage area. The latter is located outside the NPP perimeter.

The capacity of the electrolyser facility is based on the available integration locations at Rivne and Khmelnytskyi sites. The power supply for the HPP can be connected to the NPP side of the unit's transformer or to the high voltage side of the transformer. The decision will depend on the HPP size. The connection to the NPP transformer side will be limited to the availability and dimension of the internal network of each NPP.

The deliverable D2.2 "Impact assessment" has been issued and is divided into two sub-tasks; Part A: External Hazard; and Part B: Flexible Load. According to nuclear regulatory guidelines (IAEA, 2023, 2021), those events applied to the external hazard impact assessment study comprise.

- Release of hazardous material
- External fires (jet fire and flash fire)
- External explosions (cloud explosion and vessel burst)
- Generation of projectiles (after a pressure vessel burst)

The external hazard impact assessment in NPHyCo considers the following accident scenarios: (a) confined vapour cloud explosion (VCE), (b) unconfined VCE, (c) burst explosion in the hydrogen buffer tank, and (d) projectile generation. Numerical calculations are performed for three different leak sizes applied to different locations within the electrolyser facility. The sizes comprise small (1%), medium (10%) and full-bore pipe rupture (100%). The safety calculations are performed for a HPP based on a container configuration and a building solution in order to evaluate the optimal configuration from a safety perspective.

Deterministic safety calculations are performed by means of several methodologies and numerical tools.

- Implementation of semi-empirical methods in Python and MATLAB
- Numerical simulations with the lumped-parameter code COCOSYS
- Numerical simulations with the structural dynamics code AUTODYN

In order to evaluate the risk of the worst-case scenario in the HPP towards safety-related structures, the NPP operator has provided distances to nearby buildings and structures as well as the structural fragility criterion. Approximate distances to critical structures at both proposed integration locations displayed Fig. 4 in are gathered in Table 3.

Semi-empirical methods such as the Baker-Strehlow and Baker-Strehlow-Tang are implemented in Python and MATLAB to compute blast overpressure and impulse for confined and unconfined VCE events, whereas the TNT-Equivalence methodology is implemented for charge mass explosions. The Brode's model and Moore's methodology have been implemented to determine overpressure upon vessel burst and fragment generation, respectively. All those methodologies are reported in handbooks for the process safety (CCPS, 2010; Lees, 2005; TNO, 1996). The results and main insights from some of those safety calculations are reported in detail by Kykal et al. (2024) and Diaz-Pescador et al. (2025).

The hydrogen concentration at different volumes within the HPP upon a 100% leak scenario applied to the building configuration obtained with the COCOSYS code (Allelein et al., 2008) are displayed in Fig. 5. It should be noticed that the HPP building layout for a 30 MW plant is single storey construction with a quite open space and a significantly larger volume (factor of 40) compared to HPP container layout. Under such conditions the hydrogen dispersion occurs in a larger space which results in lower maximum hydrogen volumetric concentration assuming the same hydrogen release rates as for the container solutions. Thus, in this relation the HPP building solution is preferable. The 100% leak scenario does not exceed the lower flammability limit

Table 3
HPP distances to critical NPP structures.

Integration Site	NPP Structure	Distance
Onsite (Place N°1)	Standby Diesel Generators	45 m
	Cooling Tower #3	138 m
	Cooling Tower #4	159 m
	Cooling Tower #5	177 m
	Turbine Building	450 m
	Open Switchgear	1500 m
Offsite (Place N°2)	Nearest Village	1100 m
	Nuclear Station	1200 m

Fig. 5. COCOSYS, HPP building, leak 100 %, H₂ concentration in selected zones of the HPP building with active ventilation system and 12 times air change per hour.

(LFL) relying on active ventilation.

Another important outcome from the safety calculations is the location of the ventilation exhaust outlet ducts. The hydrogen vent outlet must be located at a safe distance from the oxygen vent outlet. Moreover, it must be located far away from ignition sources such as a high-voltage power lines, which are usually located in the area of the NPP site. The preferable approach would be to eliminate the hydrogen leakages by taking technical measures such as for example implementation of continuous piping or welded fittings instead of mechanical fittings due to the permeability of hydrogen at all pressures and choice of piping material, which prevent instantaneous large pipe ruptures.

The main outcomes from the explosion calculations against the NPP structural design criterion can be summarized as follows; under HPP integration into the protected area of Rivne NPP, damages at the nearby NPP structure or Standby Diesel Generator and at the cooling towers seem to be plausible for the burst explosion scenario of the buffer tank adjacent to the electrolyser facility; and HPP integration within the sanitary protection zone may have no effects to the NPP or the village despite the required minimum separation distances are larger than the distances between the HPP and the NPP structures.

The specific objective of Deliverable 2.2 Part B is to evaluate if coupled NPP + HPP could be used to generate new or enhance existing NPP flexible possibilities. Existing reactors are typically operated in a baseload mode; however, nuclear power plants are technically capable of flexible operation (IAEA, 2018). In Europe, France is the only country that currently performs load-following operation with their NPPs. Germany NPPs also operated in this flexible mode when their plants were in service.

Three types of flexible operating modes are accounted for in the report: primary/secondary frequency regulation and load following (IAEA, 2018). In order to replicate or improve the performance of a {NPP+HPP} hybrid system compared to the NPP, it is necessary to consider the values and requirements currently accomplished by the NPPs. Control range and ramps are dependent on the NPP rated power. Flexible operation requirements for representative power values have been determined.

From an economic perspective, the cost of electricity generated at nuclear power plants strongly increases if the capacity factor decreases and is more sensitive to the long-term operation conditions (IEA, 2020).

Technically, LTE technologies can meet primary frequency control, but they need to be designed for such purpose. The studies that conclude this, are focused on one-digit MW so, it seems that for low power NPPs the coupled electrolyser could meet the primary frequency requirements but in case of higher power, further analysis and technical development

is required.

The secondary frequency control requires less critical dynamic characteristics but longer duration. It seems that these requirements are easier to be accomplished by LTE. Finally, load following, due to the characteristics of ramps and time could lead the consortium to conclude that water electrolysers could meet the requirements for providing this service, but additional tests and analysis are required for evidence. The combination of electrolyser technologies may lead to further optimization of the HPP operation under load-follow mode. The segment principal strategy (Fang and Liang, 2019) may be carried out with a combination of AEL and PEM stacks, operating the former at full load, whereas the latter as part load. The same approach could be taken with a combination of LTE and HTE technologies. This strategy would require optimizing sizes of different components in the HPP such as transformer-rectifiers, electrolyser stacks, and balance of plant.

The last section of Deliverable 2.2 Part B evaluates the historical NPP “idle capacity” from different countries. France, Spain and Czech Republic were analysed. France reports the greater number of hours below the base load capacity, Spain is the second country in number of hours due to rising trend of prices close to zero in the spot market, or even negative. The “idle capacity” in Czech Republic tends to zero because they are starting to use flexible operation in its NPPs to integrate new renewable capacity.

Additionally, the case of Ukraine was deeply analysed focusing on Rivne and Khmelnytskyi NPPs. The Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH) was calculated for both plants by considering the associated “idle capacity” and different connection strategies. In case of Rivne, it is stated that exists a relevant quantity of “idle capacity” to be used as a stand-alone supply for hydrogen production. In case of Khmelnytskyi NPPs, this kind of reserve was not sufficient enough to be make the electrolyser run by itself.

As general conclusion from this report, it can be stated that a combined used of NPP with a HPP in a load follow mode is technically feasible and can bring advantages with regard to increasing renewables penetration.

The NPP Isar 2 (PWR) is the case of study for the German market. The thermal reactor power accounts for 3950 MW as of April 2023, with a gross power capacity of 1485 MW (1410 MW net capacity). The power generation profiles for the years 2020–2022 are displayed in Fig. 6. The hourly power variation during the three analysed operational exercises exceeds on average the 10% of the nominal power. This value constitutes the upper bound for secondary frequency control (optional), whereas 5% correspond to primary frequency control (mandatory). According to the European Utilities Requirements (EUR), German NPPs are required to provide the following services to the electrical grid: (a) replacement reserves, (b) ancillary services and (c) balancing mechanisms. Based on the behaviour observed in Fig. 6, it is plausible to conclude that the NPP operates in load-follow mode.

The power ramps for those three operational years, excluding plant outages, are also plotted in Fig. 6. The results show a power ramp amplitude of 12 MW/min (below 1% of NPP nominal power). In order to determine the technical feasibility of the hybrid {NPP + HPP} system, four commercially available LTE units are selected based on the foreseen 45 MW hydrogen cogeneration facility, with an electrolyser capacity of 30 MW. Those comprise the Siemens Silyzer-300 (PEM), NEL-4000 (PEM), Verde-3000 (AEL), and McLyzer-3200 (AEL). The main conclusion based on the technical specification of those electrolyser units is that the combination of AEL and PEM stacks to meet the 30 MW capacity would be able to follow the NPP power ramps demanded by the electricity grid.

3.3. WP3: Economic Roadmap

The Economic Roadmap comprises three deliverables, the outputs of which support the development of the final and main report of WP3: The NPHyCo Business Plan. The description of the work developed in each of

Fig. 6. Isar 2 operational data; (a) power generation profiles; (b) power ramp profiles.

these deliverables as well as the main outcomes are summarized in the following.

The techno-economic analysis performed takes as reference a European NPP (Rivne NPP). However, assumptions and hypothesis are considered, and the results could be subjected to a certain deviation from a more detailed stage of the project. In the analysis it has been modelled, not only the integration between the NPP and the HPP but also the complete hydrogen value chain, that is, compression, storage and delivery to a potential consumer. According to the proposal, two means of transport have been analysed: injection on a dedicated hydrogen pipeline and transport by means of trucks and tube-trailers. Fig. 7 depicts a scheme of the hybrid system analysed. One potential consumer detected is Rivneazot, a fertilizer plant located 159 km via road transport or 60 km direct line. Another off-taker could be a dedicated pipeline along 100 km to connect with an already existent gas duct in the border with Poland.

The analysis performed considers a levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) of 40.12 €/MWh, which is intended to represent a NPP with 10 years of LTO conditions according to several international references (Lazard, 2023).

In the deliverable D3.1 “Techno-economic cost models for NPHyCo Business Plan”, there have been defined the costs models for all the systems taking part in the hybrid system: (a) costs associated to three electrolysis technologies (AEL, PEM and SOEC) for different hydrogen rates and techno-economic projections until 2050, (b) design

modification costs per system with possibility to be coupled between facilities for a HPP of around 45 MW, (c) investment budget per degree of integration according to D1.2 scenarios definition, (d) cost models for compression, storage and transport according to the two means detailed in Fig. 7, (e) external electricity tariffs, water costs and other feedstock costs, and (f) NPPs LCOE depending on its lifetime moment.

In the deliverable D3.2 “Techno-economic incomes models for NPHyCo Business Plan. Operational strategies for nuclear powered hydrogen”, there are two main sections well differentiated. The first one is focused on possible stream revenues that could play a significant role in a NPP hybrid system. The following incomes have been evaluated: electricity dispatching in Day-ahead markets (DAM), electricity dispatching in balancing markets, oxygen selling, hydrogen selling, monetization of avoided CO₂ and Power-to-H₂-to-Power models, including capacity markets, ancillary services and hydrogen seasonal storage. Part of these incomes, as P-to-H₂-to-P, does not still have a remunerated system definition and they have been assessed from a qualitative standpoint.

In the second part of D3.2, several “what-if” scenarios have been run and analysed with two main purposes: (a) to determine the optimal hybrid system configuration and (b) to determine operational strategies that maximize the benefits of the hybrid system and minimize the costs.

To analyse the different sensitivity analysis, several simulation tools are used.

Fig. 7. Simulation diagram for hydrogen production, compression, storage and delivery by means of pipeline or trucks and tube-trailers.

- High-level calculations by using free-available economic tools (HEEP and H2A) focused on generic or conceptual designs for small to medium sized H₂ plants up to a few MW.
- CEA PERSEE tool (open source by 2025) based on Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formalism to minimize an objective cost function under environmental and technical constraints. It is a representative tool of classical methodologies for the techno-economic analysis of hybrid energy systems.
- Tecnomat OptimHyzer solution based on non-linear and proprietary source code. OptimHyzer and PERSEE are used also for determining the so-called advanced operational strategies. Additionally, OptimHyzer supports other functionalities as secondary regulation markets, renewable energy penetration and financial analysis over the whole lifetime of the plant.

The sensitivity analyses performed evaluates the following areas: degree of integration, storage, transport and delivery, type of technology and lifetime operation status. A benchmarking of all the aforementioned tools has been also performed in order to obtain the reason of obtaining differences between levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) results. This exercise has led to get additional insights about influential parameters when LCOH is calculated.

The conclusions obtained during the sensitivity analysis phase are.

- The degradation accountability, the hourly timestamp calculation and the inflation and discount rate consideration are the parameters detected as key for obtaining different results between modelling tools.
- The economic benefit of using internal electricity connection (electricity price assumed equal to LCOE) is remarkable for Rivne NPP. In general, this benefit will take place whenever the external grid costs (big consumer tariff) are higher than the NPP LCOE.
- At the time the analysis was done, the design modification cost estimation was based on a preliminary design and the electrolyzers techno-economic models were based on linear regressions. The LCOH for maximum degree integration reports a slightly increase with respect to the only electrical integration scenario. As the increase is so small, it is recommended to recalculate this scenario when more detailed information is available so no final conclusion about this topic can be reached with this analysis.

- Regarding degree of integration, the minimum LCOH for the case analysed is internal electrical connection to the NPP in case LTE and also steam coupling in case of using SOEC technology.
- Compression, storage and transportation processes represent a remarkable cost so, it is relevant to considerate the complete value chain when a project is being evaluated. For the case analysed, the minimum costs are detected for hydrogen injection in a dedicated 60 km pipeline. As general statement, the closer the consumer, the better.
- For LTE technologies, the most part of the LCOH weight is due to electricity consumption made by the electrolyser. The water consumption cost is negligible. However, for SOEC technology, the electrolyser CAPEX costs represent the highest share of hydrogen generation costs, and the electricity falls to a second position. The LCOH cost composition for PEM and SOEC technologies is depicted in Figs. 8 and 9.
- The results of all modelling tools show that currently the hydrogen produced with SOEC technology is more expensive than producing it with any of the LTE technologies. However, by year 2029, for this specific analysis, it is expected that SOEC will reach the same level of prices as PEM technology. By 2043, a LCOH of 2.5 €/kgH₂ could be obtained with SOEC, getting this value for the rest of the LTE technologies around 2046.
- It is constated that LTO conditions, that implies lower LCOE, are a favourable condition for minimize the LCOH. However, and it will be concluded in financial analysis, the economic feasibility of the hybrid system will be dependent on the electricity market prices.

The advanced operational strategies performed are based on multiple electrical connections points, hydrogen purchase agreements (delivery not guaranteed vs delivery guaranteed with penalties), photovoltaic energy penetration projection, and participation in secondary regulation markets.

The main conclusions obtained from these assessments are.

- The possibility of performing a connection not only internally with the NPP but also to the electrical national grid was analysed. However, this double connection has not reported remarkable benefits in the case analysed because of two main reasons: There is a constant internal supply assured by the NPP (Rivne has 4 units) and in Ukraine the price of external grid is based on spot markets plus an additional

Fig. 8. LCOH results for electrical integration scenario, PEM technology and hydrogen pipeline transport 60 km.

Fig. 9. LCOH results for electrical and steam integration, SOEC technology and hydrogen pipeline transport 60 km.

cost due to distribution. Only 549 h out of 8760 h, that is 6.2% of the annual hours, show a value lower than the NPP LCOE.

- In case the hydrogen delivery is not guaranteed, it is recommended to apply price-based strategy that means that, electricity should be sold above a certain DAM price and whenever the electricity price decreases, then is recommended to produce hydrogen. Although this strategy presents a higher LCOH than continuous production (6.44 €/kgH₂ vs 5.72 €/kgH₂), also “delta trading” concept should be taken into account. “Delta trading” is defined in the project as the loss of benefits for using part of the electricity to feed the electrolyser. This concept must be minimized to optimize the case from a financial standpoint. In Figs. 10 and 11, the price-based strategy has been depicted.
- In case hydrogen delivery is guaranteed and penalties applied, the best strategy is to produce whenever is possible whichever is the electricity cost. If penalties are avoided the costs are minimized.
- In case the degree of photovoltaic energy increases, the LCOH remains constant but the price from which a NPP starts to have more benefits as a hybrid system compared with just selling electricity

Fig. 10. Day-ahead market prices in Ukraine for a random week (July 23rd to 28th) of the reference year 2021.

Fig. 11. H₂ production order based on price-based strategy for a random week (July 23rd to 28th) of the reference year 2021.

becomes lower so, the photovoltaic penetration positively contributes to obtain better economic results in a hybrid system.

In the deliverable D3.3 “KPIs and assessment on nuclear H₂ economic feasibility compared with other types of H₂”, four main topics have been analysed: (a) current hydrogen production and consumption in Europe, (b) potential hydrogen market by end-use, (c) challenges for a competitive hydrogen market, from regulatory market to infrastructure and (d) comparison of between nuclear hydrogen and other means of production from several perspectives.

The main highlights of the aforementioned reports are.

- Traditional hydrogen production by means of steam methane reforming represents 91% of the European production capacity. At the end of 2022, electrolyser capacity in operation represented only a 0.3%.
- In many sectors, the hydrogen production is highly integrated in the process and the hydrogen replacement is not so easy.

- The future green hydrogen main end uses would be sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) and steel industry but also shipping, ammonia, methanol and refining. Most traditional uses require capacities over 100 MW. Therefore, in the context of the 45 MW set as base case for NPHyCo project, only smaller applications as chemicals or SAF could be potential consumers.
- Several challenges through a competitive hydrogen market have been identified: changing regulatory framework, grid reinforcement, massive storage and adapted infrastructure.
- Nuclear energy is the only source that can provide reliable, constant, carbon-free emissions hydrogen. The costs associated to its production are non-dependent on natural gas prices as grey hydrogen and the LCOH calculations envisaged for nuclear plants operating with LTO, shows the lowest costs among all the possible options.

All the previous information serves as an input for the final WP3 deliverable D3.4 “NPHyCo Business Plan”. The main goal of this document to define the nuclear hydrogen production from already existent NPPs as a new business, providing strategic and financial information about the requirements needed to obtain a successful case. The business plan (BP) analyses the following info: (a) NPP upcoming challenges, (b) timing and moment for nuclear hydrogen production, (c) solution description, (d) market analysis, (e) competitors and alternatives, (f) business model and (g) financial analysis.

The main conclusions extracted from the NPHyCo Business Plan are the following.

- The NPPs are expected to face two challenges: increasing demand of flexible operation and greater number of hours with electricity market prices close to zero and even negative prices.
- The moment for investing in nuclear hydrogen R&D and to take in place demonstration projects is now. There are still many challenges to overcome but there is a consensus that low-emissions hydrogen is a key opportunity for decarbonizing sectors and at the same time, to ensure the energy security of supply. European Commission and State Members need to make additional efforts and stimulate the conditions that could make nuclear hydrogen a reality.
- Grey hydrogen should not be a direct competitor of low carbon hydrogen if the main goal through a net zero economy is the decarbonisation.
- The financial analysis for LTE (PEM technology) shows:
 - o CO₂ monetization is a positive income, but its accountability is not decisive for a positive financial result.
 - o Higher production rates and technology maturity projection (operating date forecasted later than 2026) lead to a lower hydrogen selling prices
 - o The lowest selling price obtained is 3 €/kgH₂ (including transport) for starting operating year 2050, hydrogen rate from 6.000 kgH₂/h, hydrogen not guaranteed with price-based strategy.
 - o There are many references where the target of competitive hydrogen generation cost is established in 1–1.5 €/kgH₂. Taking into consideration the case analysis of this BP, where the LCOE considered is 40.12 €/MWh, a hydrogen selling price of 2.5 €/kgH₂ is envisaged for year 2050 for hydrogen rates from approximately 1976 kgH₂/h. From an approximately LCOE of 27 €/MWh (LTO + 20 years), it is possible to reach the target value of 1–1.5 €/kgH₂ by year 2050.
 - o The NPPs with LTO conditions, that is, with lower LCOE values are most favourable for obtaining lower hydrogen production costs (LCOH). However, the hydrogen selling values calculated for obtaining certain level of profitability do not differ irrespective of the lifetime moment of the plant.
 - o Although it is not part of the scope of the project, it can also be concluded that the transportation costs considerably increase the final hydrogen price. A green hydrogen replicated model of PPA

could also benefit NPPs and low carbon could be massively produced in a reliable way.

- The main conclusions obtained from financial analysis for HTE (SOEC technology) are:
 - o LCOH and consequently LCOHD (LCOH and delivery) for SOEC and PEM technologies tend to be quite similar from year 2030 and become lower for SOEC technology for the following years. The lowest selling price obtained is 3 €/kgH₂ (including transport) for starting operating year 2045 (the sooner) and 16.000 kgH₂/h or year 2050 and hydrogen rates from 6.000 kgH₂/h. Consequently, it is possible to obtain the aforementioned hydrogen selling price with SOEC technology earlier than with PEM technology.
 - o There are many references where the target of competitive hydrogen generation cost is established in 1–1.5 €/kgH₂. Taking into consideration the case analysis of this BP, where the LCOE considered is 40.12 €/MWh, a hydrogen selling price of 2 €/kgH₂ is envisaged for year 2050 for hydrogen rates of approximately 16,000 kgH₂/h. From an approximate LCOE of 27 €/MWh, it is possible to reach the target value of 1–1.5 €/kgH₂ by year 2050. In this case, just analyzing LCOH and modifying the LCOE is also constated that better results are expected to be obtained for SOEC technology in the medium/long term than for PEM technology.

Most of the nuclear hydrogen projects analysed (considering transport) envisage to require subventions if NPPs are intended to offer a hydrogen selling price competitive and at the same time, to report an acceptable profitability for the investors. The financing instruments recently run by the European Commission through the European Hydrogen Bank and dedicated to renewable hydrogen production could be also beneficial to nuclear hydrogen production and it would be an effective method for promoting and fostering nuclear-hydrogen production.

3.4. WP4: Licensing Roadmap

The deliverable D4.1 “Evaluation of regulations and licensing processes” provides an analysis of the European legislation and regulations for hydrogen and nuclear facilities applied to five different European countries (four EU member states and the Ukraine). For the design and construction of a HPP, the relevant EU directives are.

- Seveso Directive
- ATEX Directive
- Pressure Equipment Directive (PED)
- Industrial Emissions Directive (IED)

The construction of a HPP near the NPP will mostly have influence on the NPP safety and on the license, depending on the distance and the utilities and systems shared. Various cases have been addressed.

- A HPP in the vicinity of the NPP but not on the NPP site may have impact on the NPP license. This will depend on the distance of the HPP to the NPP. The HPP should be outside the sanitary zone and/or risk contour of the NPP (where specific activities are prohibited) and the safety distance of the HPP should be smaller than the distance to the NPP. If those restrictions are fulfilled, the HPP needs its own license and no impact on the NPP license is to be expected.
- In the case of a HPP on the NPP site without any coupling or integration, the hydrogen activities need to be incorporated into the NPP license, which would require a license update. The license update consists of a description of the additional buildings, installations and an update of the licensed activities to include hydrogen production.
- When coupling a HPP to an NPP, a safety reassessment is required to confirm that an appropriate level of safety is maintained in case of design modification. The safety assessment should be documented in

Table 4

External events applied to the impact assessment.

Event category	Hazard for the NPP	Load characterization
Release of hazardous material	Clouds can drift towards the NPP and burn or explode	Concentration and quantity as a function of time (kg)
Explosion	Explosion pressure wave Projectiles	Local overpressure as a function of time (kPa)
Fire	Associated flames and fires Heat (thermal flux)	Maximum temperature flux and duration (kW/m ²)
Projectile	Impact damage to structures Vibration effects	Impact energy, direction and angle, missile hardness (kg, m/s)

a safety study, which should be updated to reflect the analyses and modifications made to the facility and site conditions.

- Direct sharing of the electricity produced by the NPP, while having the HPP off-site at a significant distance would impose minimal licensing changes. The HPP would simply be seen as a consumer of electricity.

The schematic representation of the licensing and regulatory framework for the approval of an NPHyCo pilot plant is depicted in Fig. 14. The left-hand column shows the three levels of plant integration defined in WP1, which led to the coupling scenarios gathered in Table 2.

The right-hand column shows the regulatory requirements for each level of plant integration, and for each one of the two facilities, as well as existing system interfaces. The main conclusions extracted from this scheme are: (a) The nuclear regulator is in general responsible and coordinates the overall licensing process, (b) an onsite HPP will fall under the nuclear license requirements, thus requires a nuclear license modification, particularly to consider using own NPP electricity needs as a feedstock to the HPP, (c) the HPP regulatory framework is determined by the EU-directives (e.g., Euratom, Seveso, Industrial Emissions Directive, EIA, ATEX Directive), and (d) there is no specific licensing framework for hydrogen production, but it is covered by the Seveso directive for chemical plants.

The deliverable D4.2 “Safety interactions of NPP and hydrogen cogeneration” was recently completed. The outcomes from this deliverable report are restricted to the NPHyCo consortium and only a brief overview is provided in this section. The case of study in the deliverable D4.2 is based on the specifications of Rivne NPP. The deliverable report is divided into several sub-tasks.

- Identification and description of facility types (NPP/HPP) and operating conditions
- Identification and description of interaction areas between NPP and HPP and necessary system modifications and their effects on the safety of the NPP (on a technical level)
- Development and detailed description of incident/accident scenarios at the HPP and their impact on the safety of the NPP
- Detailed assessment of the various incident/accident scenarios
- Analysis of the impact of integration on the licensing and license documentation

In accordance with the integration scenarios summarized in Table 2, an overview of the HPP and NPP types within the scope of the project, and of the possible technical interfaces that resulted from the investigations performed in deliverable D2.1 was provided. From this, relevant technical operating conditions for the integration were derived and summarized on a generic level. In addition, based on exemplary information provided by the NPP operator, the necessity of technical modifications of NPP systems (e.g., electricity supply, cooling water, nitrogen supply, etc.) was determined for each integration scenario and their potential impact on nuclear safety and security was investigated. The main finding was that, in principle, no modifications of safety-related systems are required for integration, and that the necessary changes to operational systems do not affect nuclear safety or security.

The risk assessment for the various levels of plant integration is jointly carried out with the deliverable D2.2. According to IAEA (2023),

those events applied to the detailed assessment of the various incident/accident scenarios are summarized in Table 4.

The events summarized in Table 4 are evaluated by means of deterministic and probabilistic methodologies. The schematic of the applied methodology is displayed in Fig. 12. Hazardous points within the electrolyser are identified with the HAZID (HAZard IDentification) technique and system reliability analysis based on component failure rates. The identification of accident sequences in the HPP and frequency calculation is achieved with event tree analysis. In the electrolyser system, an unintended release of hydrogen may trigger a VCE, whereas in the adjacent hydrogen buffer tank a physical explosion may generate a shock wave with subsequent missile impact.

The results displayed in Fig. 13 show that the highest frequency of a

Fig. 12. Simplified schematics of the methodology applied in the impact assessment.

Fig. 13. Cumulative frequency of occurrence for the VCE scenario.

Fig. 14. Regulatory framework based on different levels of integration.

hydrogen VCE is in the order of 10^{-7} per year following a 1% leak in the separator vessel upstream flange within the gas processing area. The calculation results also show that hydrogen cloud build-up within the electrolyser facility upon delayed ignition will not exceed the LFL before the leak can be detected and isolated by the gas and leak detectors inside and outside of the electrolyser facility.

Based on the outcomes from deliverable D4.1, the necessary proof of safety to be provided for the approval of the HPP as well as necessary updates and, if necessary, extensions to the existing operating license of the NPP are evaluated. Potential implications arising from the integration levels and results from the aforementioned sub-tasks and other WPs (e.g., findings on the possible need and economic feasibility to re-dedicate natural gas pipelines or build new hydrogen pipelines to transport the hydrogen produced to consumers, scales of H_2 production, minimum distances to be maintained resulting from the safety assessment etc.) are being taken into account. Regarding the licensing of the HPP, major aspects that are being addressed are.

- Product safety
- Control of major accident hazards
- External hazards and risks
- Occupational Health and Safety
- Environmental Impact
- Emergency provisions and response organization

For many of these aspects, overlaps with the existing operating license of the NPP are expected, depending on the level of integration and the geographical location between the NPP and HPP. The operator will therefore have already developed and implemented numerous safety measures and will have to adapt these to the new operating situation. Complementary, the impact of the integration scenarios on the Safety Analysis Report underlying the NPP's existing operating license, and the resulting need to revise and update it, will be evaluated.

3.5. WP5: implementation roadmap

This WP is meant to develop the implementation plant of a pilot

nuclear-powered hydrogen cogeneration facility in an existing NPP site within Europe based on the insights from previous deliverable reports. The deliverables D5.1 "Decision Matrix for Pilot Plant" and D5.2 "Assessment of pilot plant locations and layouts" are finished. The deliverable 5.3 "Conceptual planning of pilot" is currently being developed. The outcomes are restricted to the NPHyCo consortium.

Based on the insights from previous deliverables from WP2, WP3, and WP4, the decision matrix was developed. In the decision matrix, the set of criteria was established to assist in the identification of the most suitable concept through commercial evaluation of the scenarios plus weighting of criteria. The criteria are divided into several areas: Technical (the presence of NPP sources for hydrogen production), licensing (possibility of obtaining the license on HPP either at the site of the NPP or at a nearby location), modification of the NPP (necessary technology modifications for the connection between the HPP and NPP), operational personnel (requirements for the personnel), hydrogen storage (storage capacity, storage tank type, etc), and transport of hydrogen (trucks, pipelines, etc).

In the first part of deliverable D5.2, the input data from different NPPs was collected. This data was structured according to the decision matrix. In the second part few possible scenarios for each NPP were developed, which provided the input data. These scenarios were compared according to the criteria of the decision matrix. The best scenario was selected. In Deliverable 5.3, a more detailed analysis of the selected scenario is carried out with the focus on planning the pilot project.

It is necessary to say that the Ukrainian state operator of NPPs Energoatom has shown mature interest in NPHyCo and in hosting a pilot plant with information exchange for two locations, Rivne NPP and Khmelnytskyi NPP.

4. Conclusions and outlook

This manuscript provides an overview of the NPHyCo project, highlighting the background and main outcomes at close-to-end status of the project. NPHyCo has addressed AEL, PEM and SOEC technologies, with focus on AEL and PEM given their higher TRL. Likewise, the project

has developed cases of study for all available light water technologies within Europe (PWR, BWR, VVER), with focus on VVER due to the cooperation with Energoatom with provision of NPP data. The conceptualization has delineated nine integration scenarios based on the HPP location with respect to the NPP, and the possibility of sharing auxiliaries between both facilities. The coupling scenarios are gathered in Table 2.

A reference 45 MW HPP has been established for the techno-economic and impact assessment evaluation. Regarding the external hazard impact assessment, the project results confirm that.

- The building configuration is the preferred HPP solution due to the higher dispersion efficiency of a hydrogen cloud upon unintended release
- The worst-case scenario or a hydrogen explosion within the electrolyser facility would not exceed the 10 kPa fragility criterion of the nearby safety-related NPP structures
- The highest frequency of occurrence of a VCE in the hydrogen facility accounts for 10^{-7} per year for a 1% leak. However, under such leak conditions, hydrogen concentration build-up does not exceed the LFL before detection and isolation by the gas and leak detectors
- The major risk contributor is the 30 kg hydrogen buffer tank, which must be placed outside the NPP perimeter or at an underground location
- Mitigation measures such as passive barriers are advised to minimize risk towards the NPP under HPP integration within the protected area

The flexible load impact assessment has highlighted that the HPP based on LTE technology is technically capable to follow the NPP under flexible-mode operation. The optimal HPP configuration would consist of the combination of AEL stacks (base load) and PEM stacks (part load). The same approach could be taken with a combination of LTE and HTE technologies.

From a techno-economic point of view, it has been concluded that the nuclear hybrid configurations analysed are envisaged to require subventions if NPPs are intended to offer a hydrogen selling price competitive (taking as hydrogen selling break-even price 2.5 €/kgH₂) and at the same time, to obtain a reasonable return of investment (IRR >20 % for Rivne NPP case).

Currently, the hydrogen produced with SOEC technology is more expensive than producing it with any of the LTE technologies. However, by year 2029, for this specific analysis, a trend change is expected, where the SOEC will reach the same level of prices as PEM technology. Additionally, at that time, the subventions required for a competitive hydrogen selling price will be around 2.5 €/kgH₂ with any of the technologies considered in this analysis. From 2030, the costs are expected to decrease even more, reaching a LCOH of 2.5 €/kgH₂ with SOEC by 2043 and for the rest of the LTE technologies around 2046.

In case the promising economic perspectives wants to be reached, the moment for investing in nuclear hydrogen R&D and to take in place demonstration projects is now. There are still many challenges to overcome but there is a consensus that low-emissions hydrogen is a key opportunity for decarbonizing sectors and at the same time, to ensure the energy security of supply. European Commission and State Members need to make additional efforts and stimulate the conditions that could make nuclear hydrogen a reality.

From a regulatory perspective, some of the main findings are summarized as follows.

- The nuclear regulator is in responsible and coordinates the overall licensing process
- No modifications of safety-related systems are required for integration, and the necessary changes to operational systems do not affect nuclear safety or security

- An onsite HPP will fall under the nuclear license requirements, thus requires a nuclear license modification, particularly to consider using own NPP electricity needs as a feedstock to the HPP
- The HPP regulatory framework is determined by the EU-directives (e.g., Euratom, Seveso, Industrial Emissions Directive, EIA, ATEX Directive)
- There is no specific licensing framework for hydrogen production, but it is covered by the Seveso directive for chemical plants

The implementation roadmap is in progress to develop the implementation plan of the NPHyCo pilot plant in an existing NPP site within Europe based on the insights from previous deliverables. Information about dissemination activities including the NPHyCo webinars and publicly available deliverables are provided at www.nphyco.org.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Eduard Diaz-Pescador: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Marco Viebach:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Wolfgang Lippmann:** Writing – review & editing. **Florian Gamaleja:** Writing – review & editing. **Antonio Hurtado:** Writing – review & editing. **Oleksandr Mazurok:** Writing – review & editing. **Cecilia Herrero-Moriana:** Writing – review & editing. **Martin Glöckler:** Writing – review & editing. **Stéphanie Crevon:** Writing – review & editing. **Pavla Lukášová:** Writing – review & editing. **Michael A. Fütterer:** Writing – review & editing. **Mathijs Hijlkema:** Writing – review & editing. **Gabriele Firpo:** Writing – review & editing. **Jessica Johnson:** Writing – review & editing. **Clemens Heitsch:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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